

The Hyperbolic Sieve of Prime Numbers

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Abstract: Our study initiates by introducing the HL (Hyperbolic Lattice Grid) formulated as $HL[x, y] = x * y$. This grid lays the foundation for our exploration. Subsequently, we unveil the SMT (Square Multiplication Table) as an outcome of integer coordinates within the HL in the initial quadrant. This serves as a pivotal point for our further analysis. From the SMT, we define the SMTSP (Square Multiplication Table Sieve of Primes), delving deeper into the characteristics and patterns emerging from this structure. We proceed by demonstrating the coverage of the SMT through quadratic sequences, expressed as $x = y(y \pm b)$. This expansion broadens our understanding of the relationships present within the SMT. Expanding beyond the confines of the SMT, we unveil the FMT (Full Multiplication Table), a comprehensive representation that allows us to define all integers in terms of Pairs of Complementary Divisors $(x; y)$. This distinction draws a clear line between factors and divisors, providing a deeper insight into the nature of these numerical entities. Drawing from these foundational properties, we introduce the TMTSP (Triangular Multiplication Table Sieve of Prime Numbers), which stems from the inherent characteristics of the FMT. The identification of Pairs of Complementary Divisors $(x; y)$ for integers aligns precisely with the pairs of integer coordinates (x, y) defining Cartesian points within the TMTSP on the XY-plane. This exploration leads us to assert that all integers can be categorized as either primes or composites, without exception, based on insights garnered from the multiplication table's intricacies and patterns. Notably, we establish an equivalence, or isomorphism, between the Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes and the Parabolic Sieve of Primes, demonstrating their identical outcomes.

Keywords: Sieve of prime numbers, primes and composites, multiplication table, pair of complementary divisors, hyperbolic lattice grid.

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1 Introduction

*If the number line were a river's flow,
Zero, its source, would endlessly show.
Square numbers and oblongs, two banks tall,
Guard the currents where integers sprawl.*

*All others, by the multiplication table's rules,
Swim harmoniously, akin to studying schools.
Defined by quadratic and hyperbolic laws, they glide,
In this numerical river's expansive tide.*

*Thus, they dance in rhythmic course,
Adhering to laws, their numerical force.
A picturesque scene, this mathematical play,
In the river of numbers, they find their way.*

Developing a "Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes" rooted in the multiplication table presents an intriguing endeavor. The concept of sieving primes through visual representations, as showcased in the "Parabolic Sieve of Primes" by Matiyasevich and Stechkin, offers a fascinating perspective on prime number distribution.

Creating a parallel method focusing on the hyperbolic nature inherent within the multiplication table promises to unveil unique insights into prime number patterns and distribution. Leveraging the foundational structure of the multiplication table, this pursuit aims to establish a systematic approach for identifying prime numbers within the hyperbolic framework.

The visualization and exploration of the Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes will contribute to our understanding of prime number behavior within this mathematical context, akin to its parabolic counterpart. By delving into this novel sieve, we anticipate revealing distinct patterns and characteristics governing prime numbers along the hyperbolic spectrum, offering a fresh lens through which to comprehend their distribution and relationships within the multiplication table framework.

2 The HL - Hyperbolic Lattice Grid

The process to construct the HL (Hyperbolic Lattice) Grid in the XY-plane involves two steps:

1. Drawing Circles: Plot circles in the XY-plane using the equation $x^2 + y^2 = n$, where n is a non-negative integer. Each circle corresponds to a specific value of n , and its radius is represented by $r = \sqrt{n}$.

2. Drawing Lines: For each circle with a radius $r = \sqrt{n}$, draw vertical lines at $x = r = \sqrt{n}$ and horizontal lines at $y = r = \sqrt{n}$. These lines form the grid within the circles, creating a lattice structure on the XY-plane.

Figure 1. [C000443](#) The HL - Hyperbolic Lattice Grid construction in the 1st quadrant of the XY-plane.

For circles with even values of n , use the [magenta web color #FF00FF](#).

For circles with odd values of n , use the [violet web color #7F00FF](#).

Each intersection formed by vertical lines, horizontal lines, and circles represents a point.

Assign each point a value $HL[x, y] = x * y$, which equals the product of its X and Y-coordinates.

Identify points with integer (x, y) coordinates and points with coordinates where $x = y$ along the diagonal line 45° .

Figure 2. [C000443](#) The Integers Point Products: the even points in red, the odd points in blue.

2.1 Representation:

- Even points depicted in red.
- Odd points represented in blue.
- The diagonal line at 45° in red corresponds to the diagonal of square numbers because it meets the condition $x = y$, ensuring that $x * y = x^2 = y^2$, always producing a perfect square.
- The integer coordinate points (x, y) generate the sequence found at <https://oeis.org/A000290>.

2.2 Hyperbolic Lattice Grid:

- As the entire plane is a hyperbolic lattice grid, it's possible to draw hyperbolas resulting from the products $HL[x, y] = xy = Integer$.

Figure 3. [C000443](#) The HL Hyperbolic Lattice Grid and Corresponding Hyperbolas in the 1st Quadrant.

This visual presentation showcases the HL (Hyperbolic Lattice) grid alongside its associated hyperbolas, depicted in the 1st quadrant of the Cartesian plane.

2.3 Description:

The 45-degree diagonal line, where x equals y , serves as the transverse axis encompassing all hyperbolas formulated as $HL[x, y] = xy$. These hyperbolas, characterized by the equation $HL[x, y] = xy$, are intricately interwoven within this framework.

In the visual representation, the **violet web color #7F00FF** lines are indicative of hyperbolas denoted by $HL[x, y] = xy = \frac{odd}{2} = integer \pm 0.5$. These specific hyperbolas tangentially intersect circles with radii determined by odd-number squares. Significantly, these hyperbolas intersect at least one point where either the X-coordinate or Y-coordinate equals ($integer \pm 0.5$), while the other coordinate remains an integer

Conversely, the **magenta web color #FF00FF** and red lines signify hyperbolas represented by $HL[x, y] = xy = \frac{even}{2} = integer$. These particular hyperbolas tangentially intersect circles with radii determined by even-number squares. Strikingly, these hyperbolas are the sole entities that intersect Cartesian points characterized by both X and Y coordinates being integers.

This visualization intricately illustrates the diverse interactions between the HL lattice grid, hyperbolas, and Cartesian points, delineating the distinct behaviors of odd and even hyperbolas within this mathematical construct.

3 The SMT - Square Multiplication Table

Observe the intersecting hyperbolas encompassing all the integer-coordinate Cartesian points within the XY plane. Reference the figure below to observe these intersections, where we have retained the 45° diagonal purely for reference purposes.

Figure 4. [C000443](#) The HL Hyperbolic Lattice Grid with Hyperbolas Crossing Integer Coordinates.

This visualization displays the HL (Hyperbolic Lattice) grid with hyperbolas intersecting all Cartesian points with integer coordinates within the 1st quadrant of the XY plane. The 45° diagonal line is maintained solely as a reference.

3.1 Description:

Essentially, what is being observed here precisely reflects the multiplication table within the 1st quadrant of the XY plane. This arrangement characterizes the hyperbolic lattice grid of the Square Multiplication Table (SMT).

The term "SMT – Square Multiplication Table" initially appeared in OEIS records on June 25, 2001, referencing sequences <https://oeis.org/A062856> and <https://oeis.org/A062857>. It was initially mentioned as a multiplication table, with sequence <https://oeis.org/A003991> first documented in OEIS history on March 15, 1996.

For further exploration, consider the following related links: sequence <https://oeis.org/A004247> and sequence <https://oeis.org/A061017>.

For instance, consider the integer 4, which manifests three points with integer coordinates in this 1st quadrant:

$$(x, y) = (\sqrt{1}, \sqrt{16}) = (1, 4), \text{ where } HL[x, y] = 1 * 4 = 4.$$

$$(x, y) = (\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4}) = (2, 2), \text{ where } HL[x, y] = 2 * 2 = 4.$$

$$(x, y) = (\sqrt{16}, \sqrt{1}) = (4, 1), \text{ where } HL[x, y] = 4 * 1 = 4.$$

The transverse axis, the 45° diagonal $x = y$, serves as the symmetry line for the HL hyperbolic lattice grid in both the 1st and 3rd quadrants of the XY plane.

This transverse axis distinctly illustrates why only perfect square numbers possess an odd number of positive divisors, while all other integers have an even number of positive divisors.

3.2 C001741 Bijection between SMT and A061017

The relationship between sequences <https://oeis.org/A027750> and <https://oeis.org/A056538> yielding <https://oeis.org/A061017> signifies a bijection between the products in the Square Multiplication Table (SMT) and <https://oeis.org/A061017>, as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5. C001741 Bijection between <https://oeis.org/A061017> and the SMT (Square Multiplication Table).

Starting from any point 0 on the X-axis or Y-axis, the pink vectors guide the path to point 1. The sequence <https://oeis.org/A061017> represents the resultant path formed by these pink vectors originating from point 1. Non-integer Cartesian coordinates are excluded from this representation.

The pink vectors, spanning from bottom to top, consistently move from element $(x * 1)$ to $(1 * (x + 1))$. Their journey initiates in row $y = 1$ and concludes at column $x = 1$.

The hyperbola trail, commencing at column $x = 1$ and culminating at row $y = 1$, connects all XY-plane elements possessing an integer value of $x * y$.

3.3 C000441 The Number of Products in SMT

The relationship between <https://oeis.org/A027750> and <https://oeis.org/A056538>, yielding <https://oeis.org/A061017>, elucidates the quantification of products within the Square Multiplication Table (SMT), as indicated in Figure 6.

	x coordinate		y coordinate		products	number of products
Tally	A027750	*	A056538	=	A061017	A000005
1	1	←*	1	=	1	1
2	1	←*	2	=	2	2
3	2	←*	1	=	2	2
4	1	←*	3	=	3	2
5	3	←*	1	=	3	2
6	1	*	4	=	4	3
7	2	←*	2	=	4	3
8	4	*	1	=	4	3
9	1	←*	5	=	5	2
10	5	←*	1	=	5	2
11	1	*	6	=	6	4
12	2	←*	3	=	6	4
13	3	←*	2	=	6	4
14	6	*	1	=	6	4
15	1	←*	7	=	7	2
16	7	←*	1	=	7	2
17	1	*	8	=	8	4
18	2	←*	4	=	8	4
19	4	←*	2	=	8	4
20	8	*	1	=	8	4
21	1	*	9	=	9	3
22	3	←*	3	=	9	3
23	9	*	1	=	9	3
24	1	*	10	=	10	4
25	2	←*	5	=	10	4
26	5	←*	2	=	10	4
27	10	*	1	=	10	4

Figure 6. C000441 The Number of Products in SMT.

Due to symmetries and hyperbolic relations between complementary pairs of divisors, the quantity of products derived from the multiplication of <https://oeis.org/A027750> and <https://oeis.org/A056538> yielding all positive integers appears repetitively in

<https://oeis.org/A061017>. Only the number 1 does not recur. The frequency of repetitions of positive integers resulting from these multiplications corresponds to sequence <https://oeis.org/A000005>.

3.4 The SMTSP – Square Multiplication Table Sieve of Primes

Each positive integer number has a unique representation in the 45° diagonal line transverse axis $x = y$ in the 1st and 3rd quadrant.

The prime numbers are only on the $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ lines. They have the hyperbolas passing through only points with integer coordinates in the form of $(1, Prime)$ or $(Prime, 1)$.

Only composite numbers have hyperbolas crossing more than 2 points with integer coordinates.

Only square numbers have integer coordinates along the diagonal of 45° . Because of that only square numbers have an odd number of divisors. All other integers that are not square numbers have an even number of divisors. Remarkably, number 0 remains a square number yet lacks a finite count of divisors. For each positive integer, there exists its corresponding negative integer counterpart, except for the number 0 itself, which lacks a distinct opposite. Being one of its own divisors, 0 stands as the sole number that cannot be bijected with its opposite. Intriguingly, in a peculiar manner, number 0 possesses an infinite number of divisors, an infinity that is of an odd quantity.

Only the square of prime numbers has hyperbolas crossing 3 points with integer coordinates.

Only the composite numbers different from the square of primes have hyperbolas crossing more than 3 points with integer coordinates.

Let us consider specific integers along the diagonal transverse axis ($x = y$):

- At the point $(x, y) = (\sqrt{0}, \sqrt{0}) = (0, 0)$ on the diagonal line $x = y$, resides the integer 0. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 0$ intersects $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ at integer coordinates and extends infinitely, marking 0 as a composite number due to its intersection with infinitely many other points possessing integer XY-coordinates.
- Similarly, at $(x, y) = (\sqrt{1}, \sqrt{1}) = (1, 1)$, the integer 1 lies on the diagonal axis. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 1$ crosses $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ at integer coordinates exclusively and does not intersect with any other point featuring integer XY-coordinates, thus establishing 1 as a prime number.
- Positioned at $(x, y) = (\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2}) = (2, 2)$ on the diagonal axis, integer 2 adheres to the same pattern. Its hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 2$ intersects $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ solely at integer coordinates without intersecting any other integer XY-coordinate point, categorizing 2 as a prime number.
- In a similar vein, integers 3, 5, and 7, located at $(x, y) = (\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3})$, $(\sqrt{5}, \sqrt{5})$, and $(\sqrt{7}, \sqrt{7})$ respectively, follow suit. Their corresponding hyperbolas $HL[x, y] = xy = 3$, $HL[x, y] = xy = 5$, and $HL[x, y] = xy = 7$ intersect $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ solely at

integer coordinates, yet they do not intersect with any other point possessing integer XY-coordinates, thereby designating 3, 5, and 7 as prime numbers.

- However, integer 4, positioned at $(x, y) = (\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4}) = (2, 2)$ along the diagonal axis, differs. Its hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 4$ intersects $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ at integer coordinates and intersects with other points featuring integer XY-coordinates, classifying 4 as a composite number.
- Continuing along this pattern, integers 6, 8, and 9 at $(x, y) = (\sqrt{6}, \sqrt{6}) = (\sqrt{8}, \sqrt{8}) = (\sqrt{9}, \sqrt{9})$ follow the characteristics of composite numbers. Their respective hyperbolas $HL[x, y] = xy = 6$, $HL[x, y] = xy = 8$, and $HL[x, y] = xy = 9$ intersect $x = 1$ and $y = 1$ at integer coordinates, intersecting with other points possessing integer XY-coordinates.
- This sequence perpetuates for all positive integers, delineating their composite or prime nature based on their interactions along the 45° diagonal transverse axis.

3.5 C001169 The SMT in Tabular Format

Presented below is the multiplication table displayed in tabular form.

20	0	20	40	60	80	100	120	140	160	180	200	220	240	260	280	300	320	340	360	380	400
19	0	19	38	57	76	95	114	133	152	171	190	209	228	247	266	285	304	323	342	361	380
18	0	18	36	54	72	90	108	126	144	162	180	198	216	234	252	270	288	306	324	342	360
17	0	17	34	51	68	85	102	119	136	153	170	187	204	221	238	255	272	289	306	323	340
16	0	16	32	48	64	80	96	112	128	144	160	176	192	208	224	240	256	272	288	304	320
15	0	15	30	45	60	75	90	105	120	135	150	165	180	195	210	225	240	255	270	285	300
14	0	14	28	42	56	70	84	98	112	126	140	154	168	182	196	210	224	238	252	266	280
13	0	13	26	39	52	65	78	91	104	117	130	143	156	169	182	195	208	221	234	247	260
12	0	12	24	36	48	60	72	84	96	108	120	132	144	156	168	180	192	204	216	228	240
11	0	11	22	33	44	55	66	77	88	99	110	121	132	143	154	165	176	187	198	209	220
10	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	110	120	130	140	150	160	170	180	190	200
9	0	9	18	27	36	45	54	63	72	81	90	99	108	117	126	135	144	153	162	171	180
8	0	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64	72	80	88	96	104	112	120	128	136	144	152	160
7	0	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	91	98	105	112	119	126	133	140
6	0	6	12	18	24	30	36	42	48	54	60	66	72	78	84	90	96	102	108	114	120
5	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100
4	0	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44	48	52	56	60	64	68	72	76	80
3	0	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60
2	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	34	36	38	40
1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20

Figure 7. C001169 The SMT in table format.

This table displays distinctive diagonal patterns inherent within the multiplication table. Originating from the 45° diagonal line of square numbers, successive parallel diagonals exhibit sequences such as the oblong numbers and the (square minus 1) numbers, maintaining this recurring sequence.

Each 45° diagonal forms a quadratic sequence, represented as (square sequence minus square number) and (oblong sequence minus oblong number).

The highlighted parabolic region within the table accentuates areas devoid of repetition along the diagonal line of square numbers. This emphasis underscores the unique numerical progressions and their interconnectedness within the structure of the multiplication table.

3.6 The Quadratic Sequences in the Form of $x = y(y \pm b)$

The structured arrangement of quadratic sequences, delineated by $x = y(y \pm b)$, becomes remarkably apparent when observing the $\pm 45^\circ$ diagonal lines stemming from squares, oblongs, and (square minus one) numbers.

Figure 8. C001169 Representation of Quadratic Lines within the SMT.

The highlighted red diagonals depict numbers structured as (square1 minus square2), while the blue diagonals represent numbers following the pattern of (oblong1 minus oblong2). Notably, only the red diagonals encompass odd numbers.

For ease of reasoning, let us assume both x and y as non-negative integers.

Here is an elucidation of the initial positive integers with their prime or composite attributes:

- Number 1, often termed the "oddest prime number" or the "first positive prime number," appears solely in the sequence $x = y(y + 0)$ of square numbers (<https://oeis.org/A000290>), absent from any other sequence in the form of $x = y(y + b)$.
- Number 2, recognized as the "second positive prime number," exclusively emerges in the sequence $x = y(y + 1)$ of oblong numbers (<https://oeis.org/A002378>), absent in any prior sequence of $x = y(y + b)$ for $0 \leq y < 1$.
- Continuing this pattern, number 3, referred to as the "third positive prime number," appears uniquely in the sequence $x = y(y + 2)$ (square minus 1) numbers (<https://oeis.org/A005563>), not found in any preceding sequence of $x = y(y + b)$ for $0 \leq y < 2$.
- Conversely, number 4, classified as a composite, is present in the sequence $x = y(y + 3)$ (oblong minus 2) numbers (<https://oeis.org/A028552>) and also in the previous sequence $x = y(y + 0)$ of squares (<https://oeis.org/A000290>).
- This pattern continues, distinctly defining primes and composites in various sequences, ultimately characterizing each number's unique properties within the context of quadratic sequences.
- Finally, the number 0 is present in all the mentioned sequences, earning the title of "the oddest composite number."

4 The FMT – Full Multiplication Table

Expanding the scope of the SMT, we extend the representation across the entire XY plane, resulting in what we term the FMT – Full Multiplication Table.

Figure 9. C000430 Depiction of Hyperbolic Lines within the FMT.

Each grid point in the table signifies the outcome of the product $x * y$. While a myriad of two-factor products construct the hyperbolic lines, the 45° diagonals intricately generate the parabolic (quadratic) sequences corresponding to composites. These sequences conform to the format of $x = y(y \pm b)$. [9][10]

Figure 10. C000430 Visualization of the FMT in Table Format.

This presentation offers an illustration of how the FMT manifests within the XY-plane.

5 Definition of Pair of Complementary Divisors

Observing the symmetry within the FMT's hyperbolic lines reveals an interesting pattern: any hyperbolic line intersecting $xy = 18$ in quadrant 1 will also cross 18 in quadrant 3, and symmetrically, a line crossing $xy = -18$ in quadrant 2 will cross -18 in quadrant 4. This inherent symmetry applies uniformly to all elements within the FMT.

Consequently, let us delve into the definition of the pair of complementary divisors arising from the FMT – the Full Multiplication Table.

A pair of complementary divisors, denoted as $(d_1; d_2)$, always maintains the condition $d_1 \leq d_2$. Acknowledging the symmetry in the FMT, swapping the signs of the divisors retains just a single pair of complementary divisors: $(d_1; d_2) = (-d_2; -d_1)$.

For instance, the number 18 features three pairs of complementary divisors: $(1; 18)$, $(2; 9)$, and $(3; 6)$, signifying its diverse divisor relationships.

Similarly, the number -18 also exhibits three pairs of complementary divisors: $(-18; 1)$, $(-9; 2)$, and $(-6; 3)$, revealing symmetrical divisor connections within negative integers.

The central pair of complementary divisors, represented as $(d_{c1}; d_{c2})$, denotes a special set satisfying $x \geq d_{c2} \geq +\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1} \geq 1$, where $d_{c1} * d_{c2} = x$, forming a positive integer sequence discernible from <https://oeis.org/A033676> and <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

Moreover, the trivial pair of complementary divisors, $(d_{t1}; d_{t2})$, adheres to the condition $d_{t2} \geq d_{t1}$ and $d_{t1} * d_{t2} = x$, encompassing a range from $-|x|$ to $|x|$ for d_{t1} and d_{t2} , considering the integer x .

The employment of pairs of complementary divisors elucidates specific equalities evident in various sequences within the FMT – Full Multiplication Table:

$$\text{https://oeis.org/A161906} * \text{https://oeis.org/A340791} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

$$\text{https://oeis.org/A319135} * \text{https://oeis.org/A161908} = \text{https://oeis.org/A340792}$$

$$\text{https://oeis.org/A027750} * \text{https://oeis.org/A056538} = \text{https://oeis.org/A061017}$$

These expressions offer insight into the dynamics discernible within the FMT's intricate patterns.

5.1 Factor vs. Divisor (Disambiguation)

The distinction between factors and divisors is crucial when considering integers. To define these terms, let us refer to the English language definitions as elucidated in sources such as Wikipedia's depiction of arithmetic operations.

Arithmetic operations		V · T · E	
Addition (+)			
term + term	}	= sum	
summand + summand			
addend + addend			
augend + addend			
Subtraction (-)			
term - term	}	= difference	
minuend - subtrahend			
Multiplication (×)			
factor × factor	}	= product	
multiplier × multiplicand			
Division (÷)			
$\frac{\text{dividend}}{\text{divisor}}$	}	= fraction	
			= quotient
$\frac{\text{numerator}}{\text{denominator}}$			
Exponentiation			
$\text{base}^{\text{exponent}}$		= power	
<i>n</i>th root (√)			
$\text{degree}^{\sqrt{\text{radicand}}}$		= root	
Logarithm (log)			
$\log_{\text{base}}$		(anti-logarithm) = logarithm	

C002800 Figure 11. Reproduction of the figure used by Wikipedia about arithmetic operations available online at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multiplication>.

Factors are the elements multiplied together to produce a given integer, for instance:

$$factor1 \times factor2 = integer1 \times integer2$$

Similarly, divisors are elements involved in a division resulting in a quotient or fraction:

$$dividend \div divisor = integer1 / integer2$$

It is crucial to distinguish between factors and divisors in terms of their reference to integer operations. 'Factors' specifically denote the numbers multiplied together to yield a product, whereas 'divisors' relate to the division of integers.

Every integer product emerges from the multiplication of two factors. When discussing these products arising from integer multiplication, it is vital to attribute them to factors instead of divisors.

Moreover, in scenarios where integer division results in a remainder of 0, it is essential to recognize that the involved number will always be a divisor and never categorized as a factor

5.2 The use of Factor vs. Divisor

For a two-factor multiplication to yield the desired integer, the two factors must be complementary divisors.

While in some instances, the divisors of an integer coincide with its factors, this isn't always the case. Consider the composite number 6, which possesses four positive divisors: {1, 2, 3, 6}. However, it is inaccurate to claim that 6 has 4 positive factors.

Number 36 can have various factor combinations like $36 = 1 * 2 * 3 * 6$ or $36 = 1 * 6 * 6 = 1 * 3 * 12$ or $36 = 1 * 36$. This complexity arises when defining 36 solely through factors or multiplication.

In contrast, considering only division provides a clear definition for any integer. For instance, number 36 exhibits precisely nine positive divisors: {1,2,3,4,6,9,12,18,36}. This set of distinct positive and/or negative divisors unambiguously defines the integer's primality.

Notably, when discussing factors, composite integers often exhibit factor repetitions, such as $36 = 6 * 6 = 2 * 2 * 3 * 3 = 1 * 1 * 1 * ... * 1 * 36$.

The count of factors alone does not conclusively define the primality of integers since any integer can always be expressed as the product of just two factors. In contrast, the count of divisors is definitive, particularly when employing the concept of complementary divisor pairs.

If we can repeat factor 1 infinitely as factors of any integer, on the other hand, we can only identify the divisor 1 once as a divisor of any integer. This insight provides an excellent opportunity to reconsider the Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic.

6 The TMTSP - Triangular Multiplication Table

The TMT - Triangular Multiplication Table, represented within the XY-plane and illustrated in Figure 12, comprises a lattice grid characterized by hyperbolic patterns. Spanning the 2nd and 3rd octants of the XY-plane, this table occupies the triangular regions positioned in the 1st and 2nd quadrants.

Figure 12. C001439 The hyperbolic lattice grid of the TMT - Triangular Multiplication Table.

Functioning as an intricate depiction of pairs of complementary divisors applicable to all integers, the TMT serves as a specialized tool in mathematical analyses. The naming of the 'TMT - Triangular Multiplication Table' in the OEIS traces its origins back to November 8, 2001, initially featured within sequences available at <https://oeis.org/A062858> and <https://oeis.org/A062859>.

6.1 The TMTSP - Triangular Multiplication Table Sieve of Primes

Description of Selected Integers in the 2nd octant of TMTSP:

1. Point $(\sqrt{0}, \sqrt{0})$ corresponds to integer 0. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 0$ intersects with uncountable other points with integer XY-coordinates besides (1,0). Hence, 0 is a composite number.
2. Point $(\sqrt{1}, \sqrt{1})$ represents integer 1. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 1$ does not intersect with any other point having integer XY-coordinates apart from (1,1). Consequently, 1 is a prime number.
3. Point $(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2})$ denotes integer 2. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 2$ does not intersect with any other point with integer XY-coordinates except (1,2). Therefore, 2 is a prime number.
4. Point $(\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{3})$ corresponds to integer 3. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 3$ does not intersect with any other point with integer XY-coordinates except (1,3). Hence, 3 is a prime number.
5. Point $(\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4})$ represents integer 4. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 4$ intersects with at least one other point with integer XY-coordinates besides (1,4). Therefore, 4 is a composite number.
6. Point $(\sqrt{5}, \sqrt{5})$ signifies integer 5. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 5$ does not intersect with any other point having integer XY-coordinates except (1,5). Thus, 5 is a prime number.
7. Point $(\sqrt{6}, \sqrt{6})$ denotes integer 6. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 6$ intersects with at least one other point with integer XY-coordinates besides (1,6). Thus, 6 is a composite number.
8. Point $(\sqrt{7}, \sqrt{7})$ represents integer 7. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 7$ does not intersect with any other point having integer XY-coordinates except (1,7). Hence, 7 is a prime number.
9. Point $(\sqrt{8}, \sqrt{8})$ corresponds to integer 8. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 8$ intersects with at least one other point with integer XY-coordinates besides (1,8). Thus, 8 is a composite number.
10. Point $(\sqrt{9}, \sqrt{9})$ signifies integer 9. The hyperbola $HL[x, y] = xy = 9$ intersects with at least one other point with integer XY-coordinates besides (1,9). Therefore, 9 is a composite number.

This pattern continues for all integers within the TMTSP, allowing identification of prime or composite nature based on their intersections in the XY-plane.

7 Conclusion

In both SMTSP and TMTSP, the outcomes regarding the primality of integers align perfectly. These outcomes mirror the properties showcased by the hyperbolic lattice-grid.

Each of these sieves, namely SMTSP and TMTSP, could be aptly labeled as a "hyperbolic sieve". Remarkably, these sieves exhibit analogous results to the "parabolic sieve" previously discovered by Matiyasevich, Yuri, and Stechkin, Boris in their work titled "A Visual Sieve for Prime Numbers" from 1999, which is available online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.gif>.

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